

National Aeronautics and Space
Administration

**NASA TECHNOLOGY
TRANSFER PROGRAM**

BRINGING NASA TECHNOLOGY DOWN TO EARTH

Navigating the Process of SOFTWARE RELEASE

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Ames Software Release
Authority

www.nasa.gov

Why the Software Release Review Process is Important

NASA TECHNOLOGY
TRANSFER PROGRAM

- Just as any other technology, NASA's software tools need to be tracked and utilized to their full potential. Approximately 30% of all reported NASA technologies are software-based.
- Per NASA Procedural Requirements, NPR 2210.1E, "Release of NASA Software," all NASA software products must meet the legal requirements and engineering standards that represent the agency's best practices for software development.
- An effective software release process guarantees that all software undergoes an export control review, an intellectual property review, and a commercialization assessment.
- Software release is a critical component of NASA's congressionally mandated technology transfer responsibility. Your software could have other applications in American industry, academia, and other government agencies.

NPR 2210.1E “Release of NASA Software”

Purpose

The NASA Procedural Requirements (NPR) establishes procedures and responsibilities for the reporting, review, assessment, and release of software created by, or for, NASA. These procedures reinforce that NASA software is reported and released, both internally and externally, according to law and NASA policies, with appropriate restrictions on the use and redistribution of the software. The unrestricted release of NASA software, (defined in Appendix A), is prohibited.

Applicability

This NPR is applicable to NASA Headquarters and Centers, including Component Facilities, including JPL to the extent required by its contract.

**NASA
Procedural
Requirements****NPR 2210.1E**
Effective Date: June 14, 2023
Expiration Date: June 14, 2028

COMPLIANCE IS MANDATORY FOR NASA EMPLOYEES

Release of NASA Software

Responsible Office: Space Technology Mission Directorate

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- 1.9 Center Software Release Authority
- 1.8 Center Technology Transfer Officer
- 1.7 Office of Communications
- 1.6 NASA Chief Information Security Officer (CISO)
- 1.5 NASA Inspector General

NPR 2210.1E “Release of NASA Software” (cont.)

Updates

- **Software Tools needed to validate scientific methodology**
- **Technical journals require such software with publication**
- **Added new para. g. “Scientific Research Demonstration Software” in P.2 [Applicability]**
- **Scientific Research Demonstration Software (SRDS)**
- **Go through narrow definition below**
- **When requirements are met, such software falls under release of STI under NPR 2200.2**

Limitations on ability to release with publication

- **Developed for purpose of supporting scientific publication**
- **Author/Management must confirm software meets requirements**
- **Release specifically excludes any underlying software related to scientific publication (which must go through NPR 2210 process)**

New Software Considerations

Scientific Research Demonstration Software – Software written to perform minor analyses of scientific concepts or experimental data that would be classified as Class E Software under NPR 7150.2. Such software is developed and used by NASA for the purpose of supporting the analysis presented within a scientific publication and has no other current NASA mission purpose at the time of publication. While the Authors/Innovators of such software are U.S. Government civil servants, such software may call third-party software scripts and libraries, but only where such scripts and libraries are provided under a permissive license that does not prohibit or qualify NASA’s use and release. Such software may not incorporate any third-party software.

- OR-

Software Documentation - Documentation and data pertaining to the development and operation of software and that explains the capabilities of the software or provides operating instructions for using the software to obtain the desired results. Software Documentation may be provided as owner’s manuals, user’s manuals, installation instructions, operating instructions, anomalies, other similar items.

Software Review Process and Procedure

Software Release is the process of taking NASA internal software and disseminating into the economy and the public...

To generate your Software Release request...

- First, submit your New Technology Report (NTR)
 - <https://invention.nasa.gov/>

The Software Release Authority is alerted and connects with the innovator to introduce the process as soon as a NTR case number is assigned.

- Then, submit a request via NASA's Software Release System (SRS)...
 - <https://softwarerelease.ndc.nasa.gov/>

Software Release Process

Software Release Authority Workflow

Note A – New Technology (NTR) and Software Release Authorization (SRRA) submission required:

- SRA sends email to developers
- Developer submits an NTR/Invention Disclosure (NF1679) to invention.nasa.gov
- Developer creates Software Release System (SRS) package to be reviewed by the SRA before submitting in SRS (softwarerelease.ndc.nasa.gov) for routing and reviews/approval

Note B – Software Release Types:

- General Public
- Open Source
- U.S. Government Purpose
- U.S. Release Only
- U.S. & Foreign Release

*See Software Release Options document for details

Note C – Reviewers for Approval:
Once release type is determined, initial approval by Software Release Authority starts reviews/approvals that may include:

- Technology Transfer Office
- IT Security Manager
- 508 Compliance Officer
- Software Engineering
- Safety & Mission Assurance (SMA)
- Patent Office/Legal Counsel

Requests for General Purpose Release requires approval from the Center Export Administrator

Note D – Software Usage Agreements:
SUAs are processed by the NASA Stennis SUA Team, however “ special case” request (i.e. Government Purpose, ITAR, etc.) can be handled by Center Software Release Teams.

NPR 2210.1E “Release of NASA Software”

Dear “Software Developer,”

“Thank you again for meeting with me today to share more details on whether your [SOFTWARE NAME] is [purely scientific research] and the purpose is [to distribute mathematical models that manipulate input data to detect anomalies and show it] for a paper. Thanks for providing clarity that [SOFTWARE NAME] is being released for the sole purpose of your published paper.

Per the current NPR 2210.1E (attached), please review the definitions cited in excerpts from *Appendix A. Definitions* in the attached NPR 2210.1E “Release of NASA Software,” to confirm what [SOFTWARE NAME] falls under:

Scientific Research Demonstration Software - Software written to perform minor analyses of scientific concepts or experimental data that would be classified as Class E Software under NPR 7150.2. Such software is developed and used by NASA for the purpose of supporting the analysis presented within a scientific publication and has no other current NASA mission purpose at the time of publication. While the Authors/Innovators of such software are U.S. Government civil servants, such software may call third-party software scripts and libraries, but only where such scripts and libraries are provided under a permissive license that does not prohibit or qualify NASA’s use and release. Such software may not incorporate any third-party software.

- OR -

Software Documentation - Documentation and data pertaining to the development and operation of software and that explains the capabilities of the software of provides operating instructions for using the software to obtain the desired results. Software Documentation may be provided as owner’s manuals, user’s manuals, installation instructions, operating instructions, anomalies, other similar items.

Software Documentation may include design details, algorithms, processes, procedures, rules, flow charts, formulae, and related information that would enable particular NASA software, or functional equivalentsthereof, to be reproduced or created. Premature release of such information may jeopardize intellectual property protection and commercialization of the software to which it relates. **Thus, it is advisable that such information is not released unless the Patent or IP Counsel has approved the software for release.**

Per section P.2 Applicability, see the following:

g. This NPR does not apply to Scientific Research Demonstration Software (as defined in Appendix A) that is developed and used for the purpose of supporting a scientific publication. Such publication-related software may be released with the scientific publication, but, as part of the NPR 2200.2, Requirements for Documentation, Approval and Dissemination of Scientific and Technical Information, review process for dissemination of scientific and technical information, the author/management is responsible to confirm that the related software meets the requirements set forth in the definition of Scientific Research Demonstration Software. **The ability to distribute such software under NPR 2200.2 does not also permit the inclusion or release of any underlying software that may be related to the subject of the scientific publication, which would still need to be reported and released under NPR 2210.**

h. **This NPR does not apply to computer databases, websites, or software documentation**, as defined in Appendix A unless such documentation discloses software source code.

If the above definitions (per the NPR, attached) confirm applicability for release under the NPR, we will continue with the process of completing our review in the Software Release System, for final approvals.

What Is the Software Release System (SRS)?

The SRS is the latest innovation designed to prepare your software for release. The system:

- Provides developers with a single platform to ready their software for release to the users who need it
- Employs a simple online questionnaire to replace multiple forms used previously
- Allows software packages to be reviewed concurrently by all necessary reviewers

Previous process

Streamlined Review Cycle of SRS

NASA Software Release System: Getting Started

- Log in at <https://softwarerelease.ndc.nasa.gov>
- The SRS will give you three options to select.
- During the review, you can track the progress on the Developer Dashboard

A screenshot of the NASA Software Release System (SRS) homepage. The page has a blue header with the SRS logo and the text "Software Release System". In the top right corner of the header, there is a "Dashboard" link and the user name "JACOB PARSONS". The main content area is white and contains a welcome message: "Welcome to the NASA Software Release System." followed by a paragraph explaining the system's purpose. At the bottom of the main content area, there are three blue buttons: "Submit New Release Request", "Learn about SRS", and "Go To Request Dashboard". A red arrow from the text "Developer Dashboard" in the list above points to the "Dashboard" link in the screenshot.

Who reviews my software? And what is their role?

Technology Transfer Office

- Screen request/coordinate approval and make commercialization determination

Office of Patent Counsel

- Determines IP ownership, copyrights, software provenance, and reviews 3rd party code license

508 Compliance

- Determines if software is safe and accessible for people with disabilities.

NPR 7150.2 Compliance

- NASA Software Engineering Requirements

Export Control/ IT Security

- Ensures software is safe to share with external entities

Release Categories

<https://software.nasa.gov>

Release Types

- **US/Government Purpose Only**
 - **US and Foreign**
 - **Beta Test**
 - **General Public Purpose**
 - **Open Source**
- (also, on <https://code.nasa.gov/>)

**All, but Open Source require a Software Usage Agreement (SUA) for requestors.*

Resources within Software Release (at Ames)

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